

Data-driven grasp synthesis from human demonstrations

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Abstract—With advancements in robot intelligence, they can now operate in real-world environments, but improvements in manipulation and grasping capabilities are still necessary. This work presents our research within various European projects, focusing on enhancing robot manipulation in unstructured and dynamic settings, specifically addressing the challenge of grasp synthesis for unknown objects. We developed a data-driven grasp planning algorithm that utilizes a small set of human demonstrations to transfer human operator skills to the robot for grasping previously unseen objects. By decomposing objects into basic shapes, our algorithm generates candidate grasps that can be applied to different object geometries. A selection policy, guided by a novel grasp quality metric introduced in this work, determines the most suitable grasp based on the interdependencies between the predicted grasp, the local approximation from shape decomposition, and the gripper used.

I. INTRODUCTION

Humans possess a natural ability to grasp and manipulate objects effortlessly, while current robotic manipulation and grasping capabilities fall behind, limiting the development of versatile robots for unstructured environments [1]. The robotics community focuses on grasp planning for unknown objects, with grasp planning methods divided into analytical and data-driven approaches. Analytical methods lack flexibility when the object’s geometry and physics are unknown while data-driven approaches offer greater flexibility and performance in uncertain settings. However, these approaches require large training datasets, and thus time to collect those data, to handle novel objects and complex grippers. The challenge lies in developing lightweight and data-efficient algorithms that can adapt to various grippers and synthesize valid grasps for diverse objects.

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Fig. 1. Schematic pipeline of the approach developed in [2].

In this work, we present the results of the research we carried out in the framework of several European projects to enhance manipulation capabilities of robots operating in unstructured/dynamic environments. In this context, we present the data-driven grasp planning algorithm developed in [2], which is able to generate grasps for unknown objects with different grippers. The method leverages and extend the approach presented in [3], and only requires a limited set of human demonstrations of grasps, composed of 6-DoF hand poses and interaction forces, of basic shapes. The collected demonstrations are used to learn a model used for grasp synthesis.

II. PROPOSED SOLUTION

The approach, shown in Fig. 1, starts with the acquisition of a point cloud of the target object. The cloud is decomposed into a generic number N of minimum volume bounding boxes. Secondly, exploiting a Decision Regressor Tree (DTR) trained on recorded data of a skilled human grasping sample boxes with the same gripper, a set of candidate grasps is generated from the obtained box decomposition. These poses are then ranked according to a specific metric, that takes into consideration the geometry and properties of the robotic gripper and an estimate of the interaction forces, and the best grasp is selected for execution.

A. Learning from human demonstrations

One of the main feature of the approach is the exploitation of human grasping skills to let the robot learn human-like poses for the specific gripper used. First, we collected a small set of grasp demonstrations from a human operator. Following [3], the recorded set of successful grasping attempts is used to let the robot learn a model $\mathbf{p} = \psi(\lambda_{\mathbf{b}})$ to predict a human-like pose $\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^6$ (relative to the box), given the box dimensions $\lambda_{\mathbf{b}}$. In [3] this

